

**ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE AND ITS IMPACT
TOWARDS EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN MADURAI
MEENAKSHI TEXTILE (P) LTD., DINDIGUL DISTRICT,
TAMIL NADU, INDIA: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY**

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Abstract:

The Paper has been done in Madurai Meenakshi Textile (P) Ltd., Dindigul District, Tamil Nadu. The title of the Paper is "A Study on Organizational Climate and Its Impact towards Employee Performance". The main objective of the study to find the overall knows the present working environment of the organization. And study the attitude of the employees towards existing organizational climate in Madurai Meenakshi Textile (p) Ltd. And study the impact of organization climate on employee commitments. Those data has been collected from the employees, data collected were analyzed with the statistical tool of descriptive analysis and percentage analysis and interpreted. It reflects the thoughts of researcher in the form of findings, suggestions and conclusions.

About Madurai Meenakshi Textile (P) Ltd:

Madurai Meenakshi textile (P) ltd is located at Uluppakudi village, Dindigul District. Covering 9.6 acres including building. It was registered in June 1992 and started its commercial production in December of the same year. The company started with four directors. The objective of the company is "cotton yarn polyester spinning". The finished goods are marked mainly in National market places such as "Mumbai, Ahmadabad, Surath, Karachi". There are laborers' are 78 in that time in that 48 were women and 30 were men. Madurai Meenakshi textile private limited company registered with the registrar of companies, Tamil Nadu, Chennai with registration no. 130297 on 27.6.1991. Mr. N. Lakshmanan is the chairman of the concern. He is from Uluppagudi village near Punnapatti. He is a kind hearted person with helping nature. He visits the company weekly once and absorbs the production and other activities of the company. He participates in the financial budgeting production planning for the year etc., discusses everything with the board of directors and makes the decisions related to concern. Meenakshi also takes its going-green commitment very seriously and produce over 110% of its power requirement by clean wind power. It also has a 100% governmental and legal compliance record. It manufacture 100% cotton yarn counts varying from 24s to 140s combed which goes for the manufacture of premium branded shirts and t-shirts globally. Their products are made from various imported and Indian cotton. We take pride in our contamination free cotton yarn that gives us a special niche in the market. The yarn has been widely accepted and appreciated in the industry by prominent top shirt manufactures and knitted garment manufactures, domestically and world-wide. It is well reputed for its contamination free 100% cotton ring spun & compact yarn manufactured exclusively for shirting.

Review of Literature:

Madukoma and Opeke (2001) in their study on information needs and seeking behavior of senior non-academic staff indicated that 8.70 per cent of the respondents were between 20 to 30 years of age, 45.40 per cent were between 31 to 40 years, 42.10 per cent were between 41 to 50 years of age and only 3.80 per cent were above 50 years of age.

Nurharani et al. (2004) in their study on impact of organizational climate on teachers' job performance revealed that most of the respondents (45.90%) were 27 to 35 years of age. It is also shown that 35.10 per cent respondents were 36 to 45 years old while 16.20 per cent respondents fell in the age group of below 26 years. The remaining (2.70%) respondents fell in the oldest age group of 46 to 55 years.

Okoya (2006) in her study on organizational climate and performance found that the largest single age group was between 31 and 35 years (31.30%), followed by 26.30 per cent aged between 26 and 30 years. The smallest age group accounted for 10.00 per cent and was of 35 years or less, remaining 32.30 per cent of the respondents were older than 36 years.

Pelin and Funda (2008) in their study on the effect of organizational climate on counter productive behaviors found that 64.00 per cent of the respondents were between the ages 25-34 years, followed by 18.00

percent between the ages of 35-39 years, 6.00 percent of them were older than 40 years and 12.00 percent of them were younger than 25 years.

Kadam et al. (2010) in their study on existing organizational climate in Vasantryo Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth revealed that more than half of the respondents belonged to medium age group (53.00%), followed by old age (24.00%) and 23 per cent belonged to young age group.

Suandi et al. (2012) in their study on relationship between organizational climate, job stress and job performance of officers at State Education Department found that the age groups 41 to 50 and 50 and above have a higher level of job performance as compared to the age group of 30 and below and 31 to 40. The difference in job performance is at a moderate level which is at 11 per cent. They do not find any vast difference between the age groups 41 to 50 and 50 and above and also there is no significant difference between the age groups 30 and below and 31 to 40.

Raza(2015) has been studied the impact of organizational climate on teachers performance in public and private sector company. The researcher has used two questionnaires for organization. With the support of available literature the author stated that the organizational climate is influenced by the various factors such as organization structure size, area of activity, age of members and traditional characteristic's of staff level of education, cultural level and the managerial style. The study also explained that the transitional leadership gives emphasis on motivation and helps the employees and should be followed by the organization for the attainment of objectives.

Prasad (2018) studied the personality and the relative elements of Employees satisfaction namely age and experience. In the study he concluded that the age of professionals had no effect on Employees satisfaction while Employees satisfaction increase with the frequencies of experience thereby showing significant relation with the Employee satisfaction.

Kapoor and Rao (2020) had examined the age and studied towards officers in understanding the organizational climate. His research highlighted that female employee and married female employee having more than twenty five years of age always oppose against injustice and struggle against management too.

Statement of the Problem:

Organizational climate is essential for the smooth running and functioning of an organization. An organization's HR department assumes responsibility for the effective running of the organizational climate for the benefit of their employees. So, the investigator has made an attempt in this regard and has undertaken the current study to analyze the present organizational climate in the organization and how far the employees are satisfied with the present climate in the organization and do they require any changes in the present process followed which could help them in modifying and development the present situation.

Objective of Study:

Based on the conceptual discussion made above the following objectives are framed for the successful conduct of this study.

- To know the present working environment of the organization.
- To study the attitude of the employees towards existing organizational climate.
- To know about the impact of job performance to employee satisfaction.
- To understand the problem of the employees and their organizational climate on employee commitments.

Hypothesis of the Study:

It means tentative generalization of the validity of which remains to be tested. In short it deals with certain assumption made in the study.

- Null Hypothesis: A hypothesis which assumes that there is no relationship between work environment and employee performance is called null hypothesis. It is denoted by H₀
- Alternative Hypothesis: A hypothesis which assumes that there is relationship between work environment and employee performance is called Alternative hypothesis. It is denoted by H₁

Scope of the Study:

- Organizational climate is one of the factors that influence the level of performance of employees in every industry.
- The different levels of employees namely, managers and non-managers on similar organizational study is focused on organizational climate and employee performance.
- The study has selected public sector chemical companies and made an attempt to find out the perception climate factors.
- The ultimate increase in production is achieved through the performance of employees who engaged in the Manufacturing companies.

Research Design:

The research undertaken in this study is descriptive in nature. The main purpose of descriptive research is the description of state of affairs, as it exists at present. The main characteristic of this method is that the researcher has no control over variables; he can only report what has happened or what is happening.

- Population: All the employees are working in the various departments is the Population of the study.
- Sample Size: Sample size is a part of target population carefully selected to represent the population. The overall populations are 250 and sample sizes are 110 employees.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a science of studying how research is done scientifically. It is way to systematically solve the research problem by logically adopting various steps. Methodology helps to understand not only the products of scientific enquiry but the process itself. It aims to describe and analyze method, throw light on their limitations and resources clarify throw presuppositions and consequences, relating their potentialities to the twilight zone at the frontiers of knowledge.

Data Sources:

- Primary Data: The research work mainly depends on primary data which are collected from the employees those who are working in the Madurai Meenakshi Textile (P) Ltd., The primary data includes questionnaires. The primary data was collected through a well structured with close-ended questions measures at 5-point like type scale and suggestion questions.
- Secondary Data: The secondary data and information collected from records, company websites and also discussion with the management of the organization. Secondary data was also collected from journals, magazines and books and articles.

Statistical Tools Applied:

- Simple Percentage
- Chi square test
- Correlation analysis

The primary data had been collected from various departments and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. A correlations and linear regression analysis were carryout using SPSS.

Limitation of the Study:

- Though there are four units present in the organization the authorities have permitted to collect the data from the employees in a single unit which leads to get the partial opinion.
- The data collected from the internal records may suffer from limitations like incompleteness, non-availability and irregularity

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Respondents Safe Working Environment

Safe Working	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SDA	15	13.6363
DA	12	10.9090
NEUTRAL	40	36.36363
AGREE	20	18.1818
SA	23	20.9090
TOTAL	110	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

In above the table shows that safe working environment by organization 13% of the respondents strongly disagree 10% of the respondents disagree , 36% of the respondents neutral, 18% of agree and 20% of them respondents strongly agree.

Table 2: Respondents of Employee Suggestions

Employee Suggestions	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SDA	7	6.36
DA	12	10
NEUTRAL	27	24
AGREE	40	36
SA	25	23
TOTAL	110	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

In above the table shows that Employee Suggestions by organization 6% of the respondents strongly disagree 10% of the respondents disagree, 24% of the respondents neutral, 36% of agree and 23% of them respondents strongly agree.

Table 3: Respondents of Oranization Encourages on Employee

Employee Encourages	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SDA	6	5.4
DA	14	13

NEUTRAL	39	35
AGREE	25	23
SA	26	24
TOTAL	110	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

In above the table shows that Employee Encourages by organization 5% of the respondents strongly disagree 13% of the respondents disagree, 35% of the respondents neutral, 23% of agree and 24% of them respondents strongly agree.

Conclusion:

Development of organizational climate depends upon the organization behavior organizational behavior is affected by the behavior of individual employee. Individual employee's behavior is influenced by organizational climate. So it's like a chain. If organizational climate is favorable then organization will grow smoothly. On the other hand if the employees carry a positive attitude then also organizational climate can be favorable. It is upon the individual how they perceive the climate of the organization or they feel about it. Management should consider employees view points and take some continuous feedback from them so that the organizational climate can be maintained as healthy and best.

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